

IN-SITU FABRICATION AND REFINEMENT OF AL-MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED JOINTLY BY TiB₂ AND Mg₂Si PARTICLES

Shusen Wu¹, Qi Gao, Xuecheng Duan, Ping An, Shulin LÜ*

State Key Lab of Materials Processing and Die & Mould Technology, Huazhong University of
Science and Technology,
1037 Luoyu Road, Wuhan, China

¹First author email: ssw636@hust.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.hust.edu.cn>

*Corresponding author email: shulin317@hust.edu.cn

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ABSTRACT

To solve the problem that the volume fraction of in-situ TiB₂ particle in Al-matrix composite is low, the in-situ (TiB₂+Mg₂Si)/Al composites with higher particle volume fraction were fabricated successfully. The microstructure of the composites was observed by SEM and the results revealed that TiB₂ and Mg₂Si particles are relative uniformly distributed in the matrix. X-ray diffraction was introduced to confirm the formation of TiB₂ and Mg₂Si phases, and no other intermediate phases like Al₃Ti were found in the composites. The in-situ TiB₂ particles are sub-micron in size, and Mg₂Si phase is refined from Chinese script morphology to short dispersed sticks by TiB₂ particles. The refined Mg₂Si particles are under 10 μm in size and about 10% in volume fraction. Therefore the whole volume fraction of particles is about 14%~15%. The matrix grains are effectively refined. The mechanism of refinement is considered that the TiB₂ particles and Mg₂Si phases are mutually refined. The mechanical properties of the in-situ aluminum matrix composites have also been measured.

1. INTRODUCTION

The particulates reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PRAMCs) are promising materials for the application in aerospace, military and transportation devices [1, 2]. Among various potential particulate reinforcements, TiB₂ ceramic particle is portrayed to be an outstanding reinforcement in aluminum for its good thermodynamic stability, high hardness, high melting point, high modulus, high corrosion resistance and low density [3-7]. Compared with exogenously-formed processes, in-situ processes are superior because of the composite can have a better matrix–reinforcement interfacial thermodynamic stability and a clearer interface between matrix and reinforcement. Among many in-situ processes, the salt–metal reaction route has many advantages, namely: (a) The TiB₂ particles are formed in the melt with no wet problem; (b) the reaction temperature is lower than that in other reaction systems, and the size of the TiB₂ particles can be about submicron; (c) the matrix–reinforcement interface is clean and stable; (d) bulk and continuous casting of composites are possible. The following sequence is the exothermic process to form the TiB₂ particles [6, 7]:

And the TiB_2 particles can also formed by a direct reaction [17]:

But it is hard to prepare TiB_2/Al composite with a particulate volume percent higher than 5% due to the low utilization of K_2TiF_6 and KBF_4 . The limited reaction interface is also hinder the formation of high volume percent particle refinements.

The intermetallic compound Mg_2Si can be a suitable candidate for reinforcement because of its high melting temperature, low density, high hardness, low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and high elastic modulus [9, 10]. Mg_2Si phases can be easily in-situ formed by ingot metallurgy with a high volume percentage. Researches have been done about Mg_2Si/Al composite [11-13]. The equilibrium diagram of the Al- Mg_2Si system is a pseudo-eutectic section similar to that of the Al-Si binary system according to previous studies. The equilibrium diagram has been assessed by phase-diagram calculation using an Al-DATA database, as shown in Fig. 1 [14]. Although it is easy to prepare in-situ Mg_2Si/Al composite, the large Mg_2Si particle size and the brittle eutectic matrix of the composite lower the ductility and limited the reinforcement.

Fig. 1. Calculated equilibrium phase diagram of Al- Mg_2Si pseudo-binary section [14]. The pseudo-eutectic point is 13.9wt.% Mg_2Si ; the temperature range of the ternary region at this composition is between 594 and 583.5°C, and the solubility of Mg_2Si in Al at 583.5°C is 1.91 wt.%.

TiB_2 particles has been proved that it can act as the nuclei of the primary Mg_2Si and has a good lattice matching coherence relationship with Mg_2Si , and the disregistry is only 4.64% [15]. Thus TiB_2 particles can refine and modify the primary Mg_2Si . By the combination of the salt-metal reaction route and ingot metallurgy, a mixture reinforced composite with 5vol% TiB_2 particles and 10vol% Mg_2Si phases is successfully synthesized in present. With the mixture of TiB_2 particles and Mg_2Si , the volume percentage of reinforcement is increased. The distribution of TiB_2 particles and Mg_2Si is studied and the mechanism of the TiB_2 & Mg_2Si mutual refinement is discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

In the present experiment, commercial pure Al (99.8%, wt%, the same below), pure Mg (99.9%) and Al-24.5%Si master alloy were used to prepare the Al base metal and Mg₂Si phase. Potassium fluotitanate (K₂TiF₆) and potassium fluoborate (KBF₄) were used to synthesize the TiB₂ particles through the salt reaction route and these two kinds of salts were all chemical pure.

2.2 Processing

2.2.1 Preparing TiB₂/Al base composite

Firstly, aluminum ingot was melted by a resistance furnace in a graphite crucible and over heated up to 830°C. The thoroughly mixed K₂TiF₆ and KBF₄ salts were then added into the melt with flux after 2h preheating at 300°C. Two kinds of salt powders were mixed with a molar ratio of Ti/B = 1/2, and the total mass of salts is set to synthesize 5vol% TiB₂ particles. When the salts are being added, the temperature of the melt was controlled to avoid any big ups and downs. Mechanical stirring was introduced with a graphite stirring bar during the holding time which was set for 60min. After the reaction holding, the slag was removed and the melt was cooled down to 720°C, and casted into a permanent mould preheated at 200°C.

2.2.2 Processing TiB₂+Mg₂Si /Al composites

The TiB₂/Al base composites (or Al ingots when preparing Mg₂Si/Al composites for contrast) were firstly melted and heated to 760°C, then Al-24.5%Si master alloy and pure Mg were added into the melt with a molar ratio of Mg/Si = 2/1 for synthesize 10vol% Mg₂Si phase. Flux was added into the melt for refining and protection. The holding time was set to 20min with stirring every five minutes. After holding, the melt was cooled down to 720°C and cast into a permanent mould preheated at 200°C.

2.3 Characterization

Specimens of the composites for metallographic examination were cut from the ends of tensile test samples, then grinded, polished and etched by solution with 0.5% HF. Specimens of the TiB₂& Mg₂Si/Al composites are also etched by solution with 10% NaOH for BSE testing. An Axiovert 200MAT optical microscopes and a JSM-7600F scanning electron microscope with an IncaX-Max 50 energy dispersive X-ray analysis was employed to examine the microstructures of the composites. The BSE testing was introduced by a Nova NanoSEM 450 scanning electron microscope. A XRD-7000S X-ray diffractometer with Cu Ka radiation operated at 40 kV and 40 mA was used to identify the phases in the composites. The room temperature (25°C) tensile tests were conducted on a SHIMADZU AG-100KN tester with a 2mm/min crosshead speed. The average ultimate tensile strength (UTS) value was obtained from four samples for each specific condition.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 In-situ formation of TiB₂ particles and Mg₂Si phases

The TiB₂ particles are successfully formed by the aluminothermic reaction of a complex potassium

fluoride molten salt mixture with aluminum and the Mg_2Si phase is formed by the direct reaction of Mg and Si. Fig.2 shows the result of XRD of the Mg_2Si/Al composite, TiB_2/Al composite and TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite prepared in present work. It clearly shows that no any Al_3Ti or AlB_2 peaks can be found in the result of TiB_2/Al composite and TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite, and TiB_2 peaks can be found in both composites. It confirms the formation of TiB_2 particles and no any other intermediate phases in the TiB_2/Al composite and TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite. There are no big difference of Mg_2Si peaks in the result of Mg_2Si/Al composite and TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite which confirms the formation of Mg_2Si phase in the TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite.

Fig.2 XRD diffraction patterns of the composites formed in present work:
(a). Mg_2Si/Al composite, (b). TiB_2/Al composite, (c). TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite.

3.2 Microstructure of TiB_2/Al composite

Fig. 3 shows the metallographic microstructures of TiB_2/Al composite formed in present work. The TiB_2 particles are uniformly distributed in the matrix without large agglomerations. Most of the TiB_2 particles show a trend to distribute along the grain boundary regions and some small agglomerations can be seen at these regions.

Fig.3 Metallographic microstructures of TiB_2/Al composite:
(a). Low magnification, (b). High magnification.

Fig.4 shows the SEM microstructures of TiB₂/Al composite formed in present work. It further confirms the main trend of distribution along the grain boundary of TiB₂ particles and this trend is due to most particles are rejected by the growing solid phase at the solid/liquid interface during solidification. It is worth to note that some dispersed particles still can be found near the grain boundary regions and most of them are at a size under 0.4μm. These particles are not typical hexagonal morphology because of they are too small for a completely grown crystal.

Fig. 4 SEM microstructures of TiB₂/Al composite: (a) Low magnification, (b) High magnification.

3.3 Microstructure of Mg₂Si/Al composite

Fig. 5 Optical microstructures of Mg₂Si/Al composite: (a) Low magnification, (b) High magnification.

Fig. 6 SEM microstructures of Mg₂Si /Al composite: (a) Low magnification, (b) High magnification.

Fig. 5 shows the metallographic microstructures of Mg_2Si/Al composite formed in present work. The result shows that Mg_2Si phases are distributed at grain boundary regions with a typical pseudo-eutectic morphology. Fig. 6 shows the SEM microstructures of Mg_2Si/Al composite. It further confirms that Mg_2Si phases have a Chinese script morphology. The size of pseudo-eutectic Mg_2Si phases is over $50\mu m$.

3.4 Microstructure of TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite.

Fig.7 shows the metallographic microstructures of TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite formed in present work. It is worth to note that the typical pseudo-eutectic morphology cannot be found, all the particles and intermetallic phases are distributed along the grain boundary. No large agglomerations can be found in the whole field. The width of the agglomerations along the grain boundary regions has reduced.

Fig. 7 Optical microstructures of TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite:
(a) Low magnification, (b) High magnification.

Fig. 8 SEM microstructures of TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite:
(a). Low magnification, (b). High magnification.

Fig. 8 shows the SEM microstructures of TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite formed in present work. The sample is etched by 0.5% HF. It clearly shows that the typical pseudo-eutectic morphology of Mg_2Si phases are dismissed and only very small pseudo-eutectic regions can be found with a width under $10\mu m$. Chinese script pseudo-eutectic Mg_2Si phases are refined to short dispersed sticks under $10\mu m$ and very

refined Mg_2Si phases with a size in $1-5\mu m$ can be found in the small pseudo-eutectic regions. TiB_2 particles are found in the pseudo-eutectic regions. High magnification picture Fig. 8b shows that TiB_2 particles are distributed at the interfaces in the pseudo-eutectic regions mixed with Mg_2Si phase, thus the agglomerations along the grain boundary in the TiB_2/Al composite have been broken up after adding the Mg_2Si phases.

Fig. 9 BSE microstructures of TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite:
(a) Low magnification, (b) High magnification.

Fig. 9 shows the BSE graphs of the TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite. The sample is etched by 10% NaOH. More dispersed particles are found in the pseudo-eutectic regions with a size under $0.4\mu m$ after the agglomerations are broken up, as shown in Fig. 9. A kind of Mg_2Si particles with a size near $2\mu m$ can be found in the matrix and TiB_2 particles are embedded in these Mg_2Si particles. Fig. 10 shows the SEM microstructures of extremely tiny TiB_2 particles in the TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite. These particles are found in the small agglomerations next to the refined Mg_2Si phases. They are exposed after Mg_2Si phase are etched away by HF. The size of these particles is under 100nm. This tiny particles may be the reason of why there are still some small agglomerations next to Mg_2Si phases and have on no clear particles contours.

Fig. 10 SEM microstructures of extremely tiny TiB_2 particles:
(a). Low magnification, (b). High magnification.

According to the results above, a kind of mutual refinement is found in the TiB_2 & Mg_2Si /Al composite. After adding the Mg_2Si phases, the TiB_2 agglomerations along the grain boundary can be broken up, and the TiB_2 can refine the Mg_2Si phase to short dispersed stick phase or small pseudo-eutectic phases. When there have Mg_2Si phases, pseudo-eutectic reactions happen at the solidification. So pseudo-eutectic phases are formed at the grain boundary regions and they create many interface of pseudo-eutectic Mg_2Si phases and α -Al. TiB_2 particles are pushed to the grain boundary regions at first, then some of TiB_2 particles are further pushed to the interface of pseudo-eutectic Mg_2Si phases and α -Al. So the agglomerations which are formed during the solidification are broken up with the formation of pseudo-eutectic regions.

Meanwhile, TiB_2 has been proved to be an effective heterogeneous nuclei of Mg_2Si phases. When Mg_2Si is precipitating during the solidification, the TiB_2 particles which are pushed to the grain boundary regions can effectively refine the pseudo-eutectic Mg_2Si phases by providing a lot of heterogeneous nuclei. So some Mg_2Si phases are precipitated as primary phase and refined to short dispersed stick phase. Pseudo-eutectic reaction happens in residual Mg_2Si phases, thus pseudo-eutectic Mg_2Si phases and pseudo-eutectic regions become smaller. Refined Mg_2Si phases further break up the TiB_2 agglomerations along the grain boundary and make the distribution of the TiB_2 particles more uniform. Once again, a more uniformly distributed TiB_2 particles can more uniformly refine the Mg_2Si phases throughout the bulk melt. So a more uniformly refined TiB_2 + Mg_2Si /Al composite is formed with this kind of mutual refinement.

3.5 Grain refinement

Fig. 11 shows the metallography of grains of composites formed in present work. The grains of TiB_2 /Al composite is effectively refined compared with the Al base metal. Although the TiB_2 particles can hardly act as heterogeneous nuclei directly, these particles still can hinder the growth of α -Al grains. And the intermediate phases Al_3Ti can act as very good heterogeneous nuclei of α -Al:

The critical Ti concentration of the above peritectic reaction can be reduced from 0.15% to 0.01% with the presence of element B. Thus the grains of matrix can be effectively refined with a little amount of excess intermediate phases Al_3Ti . It is worth to note that with the addition of Mg_2Si phase, the grains of the composite get further refined, this change can be attributed to the more uniformly distributed TiB_2 particles and the primary Mg_2Si phases give a much effective hindering on grain growth, and the pseudo-eutectic reaction of Mg_2Si phases and α -Al decreases the space for further growth of the grains.

Fig. 11 Metallography of grains of composites:

(a). Al matrix (b). Mg_2Si /Al composite, (c). TiB_2 /Al composite, (d). TiB_2 + Mg_2Si /Al composite.

3.6 Mechanical properties

Table 1 shows the results of mechanical property test of the composites formed in present work. It shows that TiB₂ particles have an effective reinforcement in Al matrix and the improvements of yield stress and UTS are 80% and 123% respectively, but the ductility has a dramatic decreasing. When Mg₂Si phases are added in to Al matrix, the yield and UTS have been improved by 183% and 205% with the lost of ductility. Compared with Mg₂Si/Al composite, TiB₂+Mg₂Si/Al composite has improved by 22% in yield stress and a small increasing in UTS.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of the composites.

Specimens	Yield stress (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Ductility (%)
Al	41	66	46.33
TiB ₂ /Al	74	147	16.83
Mg ₂ Si/Al	116	201	0.65
TiB ₂ +Mg ₂ Si/Al	141	217	2.45

Compared with Al matrix, the more refined grains and the dispersed TiB₂ particles improve the yield stress of TiB₂/Al composite. According to the Hall-Petch relationship:

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 + kd^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

Where σ is the flow stress, σ_0 is the friction stress and k is the Hall-Petch coefficient, the yield stress increases with the size of grains' decreases. The dislocations line to loop around the dispersed particles by Orowan looping because of the high elastic modulus of the TiB₂ particles, thus the particles improve the yield stress of the composite. With the extremely tiny particles filled in the gaps, the particles gather along the grain boundary can effectively hinder the dislocation slip. And the refined grains delay the crack nucleation by reducing the slip length. Thus the UTS of the composite is improved.

In the situation of Mg₂Si/Al composite, the pseudo-eutectic Mg₂Si phases can hinder the dislocation slip much effectively. Therefore, the yield stress and UTS are improved by 183% and 205%. But the pseudo-eutectic Mg₂Si phases are brittle, the ductility is very low. With the mixture of TiB₂ particles and Mg₂Si phases, better mechanical properties are achieved by the mutual refinement mentioned above. More dispersed TiB₂ particles and more refined grains contribute to higher yield stress. The mixture of broken TiB₂ agglomerations and refined Mg₂Si phases at the grain boundary hinder the dislocation slip much stronger, thus improving the UTS. But the improvement of UTS in TiB₂+Mg₂Si/Al composite compared with Mg₂Si/Al composite is small, this is due to the casting defects in the present work. With the refinement of pseudo-eutectic Mg₂Si phases from over 50 μ m to under 10 μ m, the ductility of the composite has improved. But the improvement of ductility is not obvious due to the casting defects and high content of Mg₂Si phases.

Fig. 12 shows the fractography of the composites formed in present work. The fractography of the Mg₂Si/Al composite shows a typical brittle fracture. The crack mainly propagates through the large pseudo-eutectic Mg₂Si phases. The fractography of the TiB₂/Al composite shows a ductile fracture, the particles are distributed at the bottom of the dimples. Some inclusions can be found. The fractography of the TiB₂+Mg₂Si/Al composite still shows a brittle fracture. The cleavage plane are much smaller because of the refinements of Mg₂Si phases and grains.

Fig. 12 Fractography of the composites:
(a). Mg_2Si/Al composite, (b). TiB_2/Al composite, (c). TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The 5vol% TiB_2/Al composites are successfully prepared. The TiB_2 particles are uniformly distributed without intermediate phases. The size of TiB_2 particles is under $0.4\mu m$ in diameter. The grains of the matrix are effectively refined.
2. The 5vol% $TiB_2+10vol%Mg_2Si/Al$ composites are successfully prepared. TiB_2 agglomerations along the grain boundary are broken up by Mg_2Si phases. The Mg_2Si phases are refined from over $50\mu m$ to under $10\mu m$.
3. The mutual refinement mechanism of TiB_2 particles and Mg_2Si phase is proposed. TiB_2 particles act as the heterogeneous nuclei of Mg_2Si phases and refine the Mg_2Si phase. The pseudo-eutectic growth of Mg_2Si and $\alpha-Al$ break the agglomerations of TiB_2 particles.
4. The extremely tiny TiB_2 particles are found in both TiB_2/Al composites and TiB_2+Mg_2Si/Al composites. It is believed that they contribute to the formation of agglomerations without clear particles contours.
5. The mechanical properties of the composites have a great improvement by the mixture of TiB_2 particles and Mg_2Si phases. The yield stress and UTS have been improved by 244% and 229% compared with Al matrix, respectively. Compared with TiB_2/Al composite, the yield stress and UTS have been also respectively improved by 91% and 48%. But the ductility is dramatically decreased.

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